

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Building the Foundations of a New “Sure Start” in and around Education Settings
Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan to build the foundations of a new “Sure Start” in and around education settings
CoTN Schools Hub Report 4.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **Early Intervention Works.** Sure Start was making a significant difference to the educational outcomes of some of the most disadvantaged children, as well as improving health outcomes.
- **Sure Start centres’ effectiveness has been demonstrated.** Next steps should seize the opportunity to build on existing assets, connect health services into these efforts, and extend connected public services across a child’s educational journey.
- **Educational Settings can help children and families overcome the challenges they face.**
- **National level focus:**
 - The Develop a national strategy placing schools at the heart of connected and co-delivered services for children and families.
 - Mandate and facilitate holistic and collaborative working. “Whole-System”, Multi-level and interdisciplinary approaches are needed.
 - Develop strategic and governance frameworks to support schools in leveraging integrated working.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Map and develop new partnerships based around place and community.
 - Leverage community resources. They have unique knowledge that should be included in decision-making about place-based connected services.
 - Join up services at local level. In particular, connect health and education.
 - Build on Sure Start and the approaches trialled in practice, highlighted in this briefing.

The Problem: Disconnect between public services means children and young people are falling through provision ‘gaps’.

Sure Start showed how children and young people can be at the heart of their communities through providing community hubs with localised, joined-up services providing early intervention and support.

Funding for Sure Start decreased by over two-thirds and over 1,340 centres closed between 2010 and 2022

49% reduction in local authority spending on early intervention services for children and young people between 2010-11 & 2017-18.

Nearly a quarter (24%) of five-year-old children have tooth decay, with each having an average of 3-4 teeth affected.

UNICEF 2024 shows that the UK is currently performing poorly across most measures of childhood wellbeing compared to the other 30 wealthiest countries in the world.
Current services (health, education, policing, care, housing, and transport) are now at the frontline of the battle against growing levels of child poverty

What you can do at a local level

- **Map partnerships around 'place'.** Research the range of potential partners that can best support families and children in local community spaces – especially regarding schools and other services/agencies.
- **Link health and education.** Produce accessible information for parents/carers and professionals (including schools) focusing on common medical problems and how to navigate local services/systems to seek help.
- **Develop new partnerships.** Integrated Care Boards and Integrated Care Services have an outstanding opportunity for imaginative collaborations between health and other services relating to educational settings.
- **Deepen Learning from Sure Start.** Schools should widen social networks and lay the foundation for future employment by fostering essential life skills.
- **Establish local joined up services.** These can support and transform neighbourhoods and thereby life chances. They should include voluntary groups, local service providers, local business, faith groups, multi-academy trusts, local authorities, charities and others.

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
The Valley Project (based in Holme Wood)	User-led space for young people not usually engaged with formal services; provides an outlet for desire for action and prosocial environment.	Tackle Inequalities, social isolation and negative perceptions for Children and Young people.
Parent Action	Community-led social support project, largely voluntary that offers opportunity for information-sharing and personal development, providing many benefits for both mothers and children.	Combats social isolation, supports physical and mental health wellbeing, provides a safe space for mothers to speak openly about their worries and concerns.
Schools and Community Organising (Birmingham)	Citizens UK: Birmingham and schools developed a partnership to empower parents to address challenges faced by families and communities.	Created platforms to engage parents, mobilise support, dissemination of information, hosted events and directed assistance to families in need.
Schools Immigration Action Project (collaboration between London Citizens/Citizens UK and the Migrant Children's Project at CORAM Children's Legal Centre)	The partnership collaboration worked with 40 families and focused on creating a safe environment for families to share experiences and concerns and open up discussions on the barriers faced by immigrant families. The project also provided free legal advice. It provides support for primary schools in understanding the effects of immigration on school families and how to support them in navigating immigration challenges.	Evidence shows the project influenced children and young people's wellbeing and cultural integration; improved communication within families and access to services such as housing.
Education Alliance for Life Chances (EALC). Formed in Bradford after the Opportunity Areas Programme finished.	A partnership approach to providing extended and coordinated support to children and families suffering multiple disadvantages. It is partnered with the Centre for Applied Educational Research which provides an R&D capacity to support work on safeguarding, mapping trends and early identification e.g. of children with autism through analysis of Early Years Foundation Profile.	To sustain progress on social mobility through improved safeguarding and efficiencies; identifying children at increased likelihood of autism through the Early Years Foundation Stage Profile and mapping/showing trends.